

**RELATIONS BETWEEN THE BUKHARA EMIRATE
AND THE RUSSIAN EMPIRE DURING THE REIGN OF
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19211969>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 19TH March 2026Accepted: 21ST March 2026Online: 23RD March 2026**KEYWORDS***embassy relations, Azimjon Muminjonov, Habibulla Abdulov, Odilnosir Subhonkulov, A.F. Negri***ABSTRACT**

This article examines the nature of diplomatic relations between the Bukhara Emirate and the Russian Empire during the reign of Amir Haydar. It provides detailed insights into the establishment of mutual trade and embassy ties, as well as the strategic objectives pursued by both states through diplomatic correspondence.

In the first half of the 19th century, specifically during the reign of Amir Haydar, there were no permanent diplomatic missions or established treaties to regulate the ongoing relations between Bukhara and Russia. Embassies were dispatched periodically, staying in either country for months or even years to discuss trade issues and other matters, seeking official approval from the respective heads of state. These missions were typically sent to deliberate on political and economic ties or to convey information regarding significant events, with their specific objectives outlined in the Amir's royal mandates (yarliqs) [1].

Archival documents reveal that at the beginning of the 19th century, between 1801 and 1803, three embassies were sent from Bukhara to St. Petersburg. Following this period, diplomatic contact ceased for a decade. The restoration of these ties was initiated by the Governor-General of Orenburg. On March 12, 1813, following the retreat of Napoleon Bonaparte's army from Russia, the Governor-General informed the Amir of Bukhara of this victory and proposed the establishment of mutually beneficial trade relations. To incentivize Bukharan merchants, the Governor-General expressed his hope of recovering and returning goods from a caravan plundered by nomads in 1812.

Subsequently, Bukhara resumed sending embassies to St. Petersburg. The Amir's letters and mandates began to include information regarding the losses suffered by merchants due to banditry. On July 15, 1814, a formal letter from G.S. Volkonsky, the Governor-General of Orenburg, to the Russian State Chancellor N. Rumyantsev, reported the arrival of two envoys from Amir Haydar. One was an envoy traveling to Istanbul (Constantinople) to congratulate the Sultan on the end of the war and the establishment of peace in Europe; the other was Azimjon Muminjonov, a high-ranking official who remained in St. Petersburg to negotiate trade issues. These envoys reached Orenburg in the summer of 1814 and St. Petersburg in January 1815. Thus, the mission consisted of two parts: Azimjon Devonbegi, the primary envoy for Bukhara-Russia relations, and the second envoy seeking permission from the Tsar to transit through Russian territory to Turkey.

In 1818, another official embassy led by Azimjon Muminjonov was dispatched from the Bukhara Emirate to Russia. Alongside the official mandate, Amir Haydar entrusted the envoy with specific oral instructions.

Earlier, in 1805, on the orders of Prince Adam Charteriyskiy, head of the Russian Ministry of Foreign Affairs, a Russian "confidant" named Habibulla Abdulov was sent from Orenburg to Bukhara disguised as a merchant. His formal mission was to negotiate the extradition of Russian subjects (Teptyar-Tatars) who had fled to Bukhara after being accused of counterfeiting. However, his primary secret objective was to bring a presumed grandson of Nadir Shah, living in Bukhara, under the protection of the Russian Emperor. That same year, two Bukharan merchant-envoys, Mirzabek Allayorov and Gofurjon Navro'zjonov, arrived in Orenburg. They delivered tools confiscated from Valit Khamitov, a notorious counterfeiter in Bukhara, to the Governor-General. However, due to the lack of formal credentials confirming their diplomatic status, they were not permitted to meet with high-ranking Russian officials.

Nevertheless, they were treated with courtesy to maintain friendly relations with the Emirate.

In 1809, another confidant, Lieutenant Odilnosir Subhonkulov, was sent secretly to Bukhara under the supervision of the Orenburg Military Governor. Subhonkulov's mission focused on ensuring the security of caravan trade, addressing the issue of plundered caravans, and establishing cooperation between Russia and Bukhara in combating crime. A key priority was the extradition of the counterfeiter Khamitov and his accomplices, who had found refuge in Bukhara.

In response, Amir Haydar stated in his letter that such matters should only be resolved directly between the heads of state; he insisted that the Russian sovereign himself must address the Amir. By adhering to international protocol in this manner, Amir Haydar not only reminded Russia of diplomatic norms but also demonstrated his commitment to maintaining the prestige and sovereignty of the Bukhara Emirate on the international stage.

The Russian Ministry of Foreign Affairs studied the Amir's letter and decided to continue fostering good relations, recognizing the strategic opportunities offered by the Emirate. Through mutual legal assistance based on these agreements, the criminal group led by Valit Khamitov was handed over to the Russian authorities. Furthermore, Subhonkulov's mission obtained data on the routes and individuals involved in the distribution of counterfeit currency. Subhonkulov also succeeded in securing the release of three Russian prisoners held in Bukhara.

It is important to emphasize that relations during Amir Haydar's reign were not one-sided. In 1820, the first official Russian embassy, led by A.F. Negri, visited Bukhara in response to the Emirate's diplomatic efforts.

Thanks to Amir Haydar's prudent policy, the Bukhara Emirate was recognized as an independent and equal state in foreign affairs, which played a crucial role in subsequent political relations with Russia and other powers. It is noteworthy that while the Russian Empire sent agents to Bukhara—largely due to fears of Bukhara and Khiva forming an alliance or falling under French influence during the Russo-Persian wars—Amir Haydar remained well-informed of these maneuvers. He conducted his foreign policy based on the security interests of his own state rather than the provocations of colonial powers

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